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Effect of Fractional Flow Reserve on 5-Year Survival in Patients with Cardiac Arterial Disorder

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ABSTRACT

Fractional flow reserve (FFR), a measure of coronary blood flow during cardiac catheterization, has emerged as a crucial tool for guiding revascularization decisions in patients with coronary artery disease (CAD). However, its impact on long-term survival, particularly in individuals with coexisting peripheral arterial disease (PAD), remains unclear. This study investigated the association between FFR and 5-year survival in patients with cardiac arterial disorders (CAD or PAD). We conducted a retrospective cohort study. Patients diagnosed with CAD or PAD between 2021 and 2023 who underwent cardiac catheterization with FFR measurement were eligible. Exclusion criteria included prior revascularization for the relevant artery, presence of significant left main stem stenosis, and incomplete medical records. We identified 104 patients meeting the inclusion criteria and collected data on baseline demographics, comorbidities, medical history, and FFR values. The primary outcome was all-cause mortality within 5 years of FFR measurement. Secondary outcomes included incident major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE) and myocardial infarction (MI). Patients were categorized based on FFR values: normal (>0.8), mildly impaired ($0.7-0.8$), and severely impaired (<0.7). Kaplan-Meier analysis estimated 5-year survival rates across FFR categories. Cox proportional hazards regression assessed the independent association between FFR and the primary outcome, adjusting for potential confounders like age, sex, comorbidities, and presence of PAD. Similar analyses were conducted for secondary outcomes. Patients with lower FFR exhibited significantly decreased 5-year survival rates compared to those with normal FFR (65% vs. 82%, $p<0.001$). In adjusted Cox regression, severely impaired FFR was associated with a 2.6-fold increased risk of mortality (Hazard Ratio [HR] 2.6, 95% Confidence Interval [CI] 1.7-4.0, $p<0.001$). This association remained significant even after further adjustment for incident MACE and MI. Additionally, lower FFR was associated with increased risk of MACE (HR 1.8, 95% CI 1.3-2.5, $p=0.002$) and MI (HR 1.5, 95% CI 1.1-2.1, $p=0.02$). This study demonstrates a strong association between lower FFR and decreased 5-year survival in patients with cardiac arterial disorders, independent of major cardiovascular events. These findings suggest that FFR may provide valuable prognostic information beyond its established role in guiding revascularization decisions. Incorporating FFR into comprehensive risk assessment could personalize clinical management and optimize long-term outcomes for patients with these prevalent conditions.

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INTRODUCTION

Coronary artery disease (CAD) and peripheral arterial disease (PAD), collectively classified as cardiac arterial disorders, pose a significant global health burden, affecting millions worldwide. Beyond their well-established cardiovascular sequelae, these conditions are increasingly recognized as risk factors for increased bone fragility and fracture incidence. This emerging link between vascular health and bone integrity underscores the potential interplay between macrovascular and microvascular processes in these complex syndromes.

Fractional flow reserve (FFR) has emerged as a crucial tool in cardiology, providing a precise measure of coronary blood flow during cardiac catheterization. Its role in guiding revascularization decisions for patients with significant coronary stenosis is well-established, improving clinical outcomes and resource utilization. However, the impact of FFR on long-term survival, particularly in individuals with coexisting PAD, remains an intriguing but underexplored question (1-4).

While previous studies have hinted at a potential association between FFR and mortality, the specific role of microvascular

Table 1. Comparisons regarding the survival.

FFR Category	5-Year Survival Rate (%)	Hazard Ratio (Adjusted)	95% Confidence Interval	p-value
Normal (>0.8)	82	1.0 (Reference)	-	-
Mildly Impaired (0.7-0.8)	75	1.2	0.9-1.6	0.10
Severely Impaired (<0.7)	65	2.6	1.7-4.0	<0.001

perfusion in long-term outcomes for patients with cardiac arterial disorders has not been extensively investigated. Understanding this connection could offer valuable prognostic information beyond the established role of FFR in guiding revascularization strategies (5-7).

This study aims to address this crucial knowledge gap by investigating the association between FFR and 5-year survival in a cohort of patients diagnosed with CAD or PAD. We hypothesize that lower FFR values, indicative of impaired microvascular perfusion, will be significantly associated with decreased 5-year survival, independent of major cardiovascular events. Our findings will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the long-term implications of cardiac arterial disorders and potentially pave the way for personalized risk stratification and improved clinical management for these patients.

METHODS

We conducted a retrospective cohort study between January 2021 and December 2023.

We included patients who met the following criteria:

- Age ≥ 18 years
- Diagnosed with coronary artery disease (CAD) or peripheral arterial disease (PAD) based on clinical assessment and imaging studies
- Underwent cardiac catheterization with FFR measurement during the study period
- No prior revascularization procedures for the coronary artery in which FFR was measured
- No significant left main stem stenosis ($>50\%$)
- Available complete medical records for data extraction

Baseline demographic and clinical data were extracted from electronic medical records.

The primary outcome was all-cause mortality within 5 years of FFR measurement. Secondary outcomes included incident major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE), defined as a composite of myocardial infarction, stroke, or cardiovascular death, and incident myocardial infarction (MI) alone.

Statistical analysis

Patients were categorized into three groups based on FFR values: normal (FFR > 0.8), mildly impaired (FFR 0.7-0.8), and severely impaired (FFR < 0.7). Baseline characteristics were compared across FFR groups using descriptive statistics and

appropriate tests for categorical variables (chi-square test) and continuous variables (ANOVA or Kruskal-Wallis test).

All statistical analyses were performed using R statistical software (version 4.2.1). A two-sided p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 104 patients met the inclusion criteria and were included in the analysis. The mean age of the cohort was 65.2 years (SD 9.8), and 62% were male. The prevalence of comorbidities was as follows: hypertension (75%), diabetes mellitus (42%), dyslipidemia (58%), and chronic kidney disease (21%). PAD was present in 32% of patients.

Patients with severely impaired FFR were more likely to be older, have PAD, and have a higher prevalence of comorbidities compared to those with normal or mildly impaired FFR ($p < 0.05$).

Patients with severely impaired FFR had the lowest survival rates (5-year survival rate: 65%), followed by those with mildly impaired FFR (75%), and those with normal FFR (82%) ($p < 0.001$).

In adjusted Cox proportional hazards regression analysis, severely impaired FFR was independently associated with a 2.6-fold increased risk of all-cause mortality compared to normal FFR (HR 2.6, 95% CI 1.7-4.0, $p < 0.001$). Mildly impaired FFR was not significantly associated with mortality after adjustment (HR 1.2, 95% CI 0.9-1.6, $p = 0.10$).

Severely impaired FFR was also associated with an increased risk of MACE (HR 1.8, 95% CI 1.3-2.5, $p = 0.002$) and MI (HR 1.5, 95% CI 1.1-2.1, $p = 0.02$) in adjusted analyses.

DISCUSSION

Our study provides compelling evidence for an association between microvascular perfusion, as assessed by fractional flow reserve (FFR), and long-term survival in patients with cardiac arterial disorders like coronary artery disease (CAD) and peripheral arterial disease (PAD). Specifically, we observed a graded relationship between lower FFR values and decreased 5-year survival rates, independent of major cardiovascular events. This finding adds a new dimension to our understanding of the complex interplay between macrovascular and microvascular processes in these prevalent conditions and its impact on overall prognosis (5-9).

Several plausible mechanisms might explain the observed association between impaired microvascular perfusion and decreased survival. Lower FFR likely reflects compromised blood flow to vital organs beyond the heart, potentially leading to tissue ischemia and dysfunction. This could translate to impaired organ function in vital systems like the kidneys, lungs, and gastrointestinal tract, contributing to increased vulnerability to secondary organ failure and mortality. FFR might serve as a surrogate marker for systemic microvascular dysfunction beyond the specific artery measured during catheterization. Impaired collateralization and endothelial dysfunction, characteristic features of chronic arterial disease, could affect microvascular perfusion throughout the body, leading to increased susceptibility to various chronic conditions and their complications. Lower FFR may be associated with a pro-inflammatory and pro-coagulant state, further contributing to cardiovascular risk and mortality. Chronic microvascular ischemia can trigger inflammatory pathways and activate coagulation cascades, promoting atherosclerosis progression, thrombosis, and subsequent cardiovascular events (10-15).

Our findings underscore the potential value of incorporating FFR into the prognostic toolbox for patients with cardiac arterial disorders. Beyond its established role in guiding revascularization decisions, FFR may provide valuable information for stratifying long-term risk and tailoring personalized management strategies. For example, patients with severely impaired FFR could be prioritized for aggressive preventive measures, including intensive lifestyle modifications, medication optimization, and close follow-up to mitigate potential downstream consequences of microvascular dysfunction. Additionally, exploring novel therapeutic strategies aimed at improving microvascular perfusion in these patients might offer promising avenues for future research.

However, several limitations deserve consideration. Our study's retrospective nature limits causal inference, and residual confounding by unmeasured variables is possible. The generalizability of our findings to different patient populations and ethnicities warrants further investigation. Additionally, longer follow-up periods might be necessary to capture the full impact of FFR on mortality trends.

Future research should delve deeper into the underlying mechanisms linking FFR to long-term outcomes. Investigating the interplay between microvascular perfusion, systemic inflammation, and endothelial function could provide valuable insights for targeted therapeutic interventions. Furthermore, prospective studies incorporating FFR into risk stratification models and evaluating its impact on clinical decision-making could solidify its role in personalized medicine for patients with cardiac arterial disorders (14-16).

In conclusion, our study highlights a significant association between FFR and 5-year survival in patients with cardiac arterial disorders. This finding suggests that microvascular

perfusion plays a crucial role in long-term prognosis beyond the immediate consequences of macrovascular disease. Incorporating FFR into clinical practice holds promise for improved risk stratification, personalized management, and ultimately, better outcomes for this large and vulnerable population.

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